

UDC: 626.8 (075.3)

RESTORATION OF RIVER COURSES THAT LOST NATURAL STABILITY**Sabir Hasanov Tehrankhan oglu,***Doctor of Technical Sciences. Envy of the department.
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Azerbaijan Architecture and Construction University. Baku*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246938>**Abstract**

The article is devoted to the structural characteristics, principles of operation, and shortcomings of devices used to restore river channels that have lost their natural stability. It was determined that, the constructions of known sewage treatment plants are complex and their construction requires a large amount of construction materials, funds, and labor. Considering this, a drainage amelioration device called a light structure bottom net was developed. The proposed installation consists of a reinforced steel grid, tensioned steel cables, small pile supports, and connecting fastening elements. The article also proposed a calculation method for determining the recovery period of the damaged duct. It was determined that, flood flows play a very large role in the process of rehabilitation. Thus, it is possible to restore the river channel with a length of 4500 m, a width of 30 m, and a deformation depth of 9 m due to the bottom net within 7 hours due to the flood. However, in the normal case, that is, in the absence of flood flow, it takes 37.1 years to restore the channel.

Keywords: river, course, restoration, installation, bottom net, bringing, durability, duration.

Introduction. Rivers have been subjected to strong anthropogenic influences according to the observations and specific studies conducted on rivers in Azerbaijan. The coastal and water protection zones of the rivers are heavily populated, numerous industrial, agricultural, domestic, and recreational facilities have been built. Simultaneously, sand and gravel quarries were opened in the course of the rivers and the riparian zones, and the rivers were mercilessly exploited. 64 rivers with a length of more than 50 km flow in the territory of Azerbaijan. More than 255 sand and gravel quarries operate on these rivers. Quarries from 5 to 40 are located on one river. For example, there are 40 quarries on the Velvalachay River, 26 on the Garachay River, 17 on the Gudyalchay River, and 5 on the Gusarchay River, which flows on the northeastern slope of the Greater Caucasus. As a result of quarries, the alluvial layer in river beds has been completely depleted and rivers have lost their natural beds. A new type of channel has been formed as a result of external interventions in rivers and changes in its flow regime. Rivers have created a new bed in the base erosion layer. The process of deformation in the channel has intensified in terms of depth and plan, and as a result, the bottom of the rivers dropped by an average of 5-25 m, and the coastline shifted up to 100-200 m due to washing. According to the conducted studies, the bottom of the 200 km long Tartar River has dropped 6-10 m as a result of deformation in depth and plan due to external interventions and quarries, and the coastline has shifted more than 100 m. In 4.5 km of Goychay river, which is 115 km long, the river bed has dropped by 10 m, its banks were washed away and widened by 80-90 m. 10.68 km of Karachay River was washed away and subjected to depth deformation from 5 m to 25 m. The analysis of the scale of anthropogenic impacts on rivers shows that self-recovery of seriously degraded rivers is

a very long process. According to calculations rivers that have lost their natural stability may take 100 years or more to restore themselves. Therefore, it is necessary to use sewage treatment facilities.

The object of research is river channels and river rehabilitation facilities that have lost their natural stability.

Research methodology. Information was collected about the devices used and developed to restore the river channels that have lost their stability, involved in scientific analysis, their constructions and working principles studied, and advantages and disadvantages identified. Simultaneously, channel processes were analyzed based on the laws of hydraulics, and relevant conclusions were drawn. Based on the obtained actual, experimental materials and theoretical judgments, a new drainage device-bottom net was developed.

Analysis and discussions. Hydro-technical devices, drainage works are divided into two parts in the practice of applying: 1) regulation of rivers completely 2) channel restoration in separate areas of rivers. In the first case, a long time and a large amount of funds are required for the restoration and regulation of river channels. Therefore, restoration and regulation measures should be implemented in separate areas of the rivers (in the most deformed and degraded places) in order to solve the problem, and they should be included in the river's main plan.

In the classic sources of hydrotechnical facilities [1,2,3,4,5,6, etc.], restoration of river channels is not considered a separate field. In this direction, channel issues such as river alignment, fight against local erosion, fight against encroachment, fight against sediments, protection of coastal zones from flooding, strengthening of river banks, fight against floods, and regulation of flows are looked through separately. However, in recent years, the destructive anthropogenic effects on

river channels have led to the formation of a new scientific direction on the practice of hydrotechnical facilities - the concept of river restoration.

As a result of Sh. Sh. Guliyev's [7] research in 2006-2008 determined that the country's rivers, especially those exploited under the activity of sand-gravel quarries, were not capable of restoring their course by themselves in a natural way. The author inferred that it is necessary to implement complex hydrotechnical measures to restore the channels of rivers that have lost their natural stability. It has been offered to restore the 42 km channel of the Valvalachay River by strengthening the banks, increasing the river's width, laying stones on the river bed, and creating a new channel [8].

A channel restoration scheme has been prepared by Sh.S. Guliyev [9] to restore the course of rivers that have lost their natural stability. The main essence of this scheme is that the spillways are built in the eroded channel, the connection between one side of the canal with the flood-lands cut off with a retaining wall, a new canal is created on the other side of the flood-lands, and its bed paved with stones. Concrete, stone-concrete, reinforced concrete retaining walls, the earth-filled dam covered with concrete and reinforced concrete, the earth-filled dam strengthened with gabions, the earth-filled dam reinforced with masonry, and stone embankments are used to strengthen the embankments.

Sh.Sh. Guliyev and Kh.Sh. Shahsuvarli [10] proposed a channel flood-lands and water intake embankment-type sewer rehabilitation scheme. In this scheme, the main course of the river is paved with stone, on one of the flood-lands shores, a closed canal is being constructed, consisting of retaining walls made of reinforced concrete and other materials, on the other side of the flood-lands bank and channel, a single-row bank strengthening device is created from the same element. One side of the river receives flood waters and is transported by a closed canal. When the flood waters enter the other bank of the river, it is prevented from entering the adjacent areas with the help of a retaining wall. The offered sewage rehabilitation scheme can be applied in special circumstances.

B.M. Ahmadov, I.H. Agayev and A.M. Muslimov [11] designed a sloping dam (weir) to collapse the flow of floods and torrents, to change the longitudinal profile of the river, and to increase the stability of the river channel. The proposed device consists of an inclined drainage wall, slits permeable to water opened on the wall, a water diverter placed at the bottom of the slits, and a flooded part. Slope weir dams can be applied in the eroded part of the river. However, the fact that it is a single device may not have the desired effect during sewer restoration. It is more appropriate to combine it with other devices.

B.M. Ahmadov, I.H. Agayev and A.M. Muslimov [11] proposed a joint arrangement of new constructions of semi-fine and embankment devices to protect the river banks and their beds from washing away. The semi-weir device is placed in front of the coastal protection device at a certain angle to the direction of flow. During such arrangement, the impact force and speed of the flow falling towards the coastal protection device is reduced. However, the proposed arrangement can be

used in drainage works in the bends of deformed mountain rivers.

A.M. Muslimov, M.I. Mahmudova and R.C. Rustamov [12] developed a barrage type device for restoring and increasing the stability of a channel that has lost its natural stability. The proposed barrage structure consists of a fixed-radius arch-shaped barrage section, a spillway located on it, a straight barrage wall located on the left and right sides of the arch-shaped barrage wall, a flooded section, a retaining wall, retaining longitudinal partition walls, sections filled with large river stones and embankment reinforcement. The shortcoming of the proposed dam-type weir consists of being inevitable that the porous sections of the device will quickly become clogged with mud and other debris during floods. This device has the ability to restore a part of the canal that has lost its stability. If the length of the damaged canal is long, it is not possible to restore other parts of the canal. That's why it is required to build additional weirs.

In contrast to the above-described barrage-type weir device, A.M. Muslimov, B.M. Ahmadov and M.I. Mahmudova [13] developed a more advanced system of reinforcing weirs. According to the authors, the newly designed weirs distribute the flow effect evenly across the channel width by breaking up the core of the flow. It leads to an increase in the stability of both the device and the channel. The authors' conclusion is justified in the straight course of the river. However, it is difficult to get this effect in curved and winding areas of rivers. Simultaneously, while breaking the core of the flow with an arch-shaped spillway, its influence is directed toward the shores. A large velocity is created at the bottom of the embankment and it can lead to the washing of the bottom of the embankment and the loss of its stability.

Analysis shows that the construction of weirs in river channels causes the rise of the river bed and the water level in the river, but it leads to the width of the channel increases. At this time, the danger of inundation of the areas adjacent to the river increases. On the other hand, the construction of weirs is more expensive than the bottom threshold and after a while, after being completely filled with new channels, the weirs remain under the sediments and complete their functions.

In general, the issue of restoring the course of rivers that have lost stability should be solved in a complex way. While solving the problem, the usage of a combination of several hydrotechnical device arrangements makes it possible to develop more effective drainage devices.

We have developed a channel restoration device that differs from its predecessors in terms of its constructive solution to restore river channels that have lost their natural stability as a result of anthropogenic influences.

We have developed a lighter construction, durable, and low-cost bottom channel restoration device to restore the river channels by catching the sediments of the flow. This channel restoration device consists of a reinforced steel grid, tensioned steel cables, small piles, and connecting elements (picture).

This is exactly how the proposed channel restoration device works. Piles made of reinforced concrete or steel pipes are driven across the width of the river at certain distances in the section of the river where the channel has been lost. Holes are opened at the top, middle, and bottom sides of the piles. Steel ropes are passed through the holes of the middle piles and their ends are firmly connected by connecting elements to the piles built on the banks of the river. A steel net is placed in front of the steel ropes and tied to them. One end of the connecting element is made in the form of a break or

loop, and the other end is made as a threaded bolt, and a nut is attached to it.

The channel restoration device is built in several places along the length of the deformed (bottom washed out and lowered) river bed. The distance between the devices is determined by the following formula according to the depth of the washed bottom layer (h) and the slope of the bottom river (i_d):

$$L = \frac{h}{i_d} \tag{1}$$

The proposed bottom grid works like this.

Picture. A bottom net that restores the river bed:

1- net; 2- rope; 3- pile-support; 4-anchor; FWL- flood water level; NWL-normal water level; RBL- recoverable bottom level of the river; DBL- deformed bottom level of the river; L-distance between bottom nets

When torrent and flood flows pass through the facility, some of the large and solid materials brought by them (gravel, pebbles, stone, rock fragments, tree stumps, etc. extraneous objects) are caught and stored through the net, and the other part gets stuck in the next

net. After a certain period, sedimentation and accumulation of river sediments occur along the deformed channel. As a result, the washed and deformed bottom level of the river gradually rises and takes its initial

state. Thus, the river channel, which has lost its stability, is restored.

The proposed channel restoration devices are in permanent operation. Their maintenance costs are not required. These facilities are not only channel restoration devices, they also work as torrent and flood protection devices that prevent the harmful effects of torrents and floodwaters.

Flows in hydrometry are mainly expressed in kg/sec. This includes bottom and floating (dependent) fetches. The flow rate G can be used to determine how long it will take for the space between the bottom channel restoration devices to be completely filled with flow. Let's say that the average annual consumption in the river is known. The consequent volume due to this import cost will be expressed as follows:

$$W_g = \frac{G}{\gamma} t, \quad (2)$$

where W_g is the volume of the fetches that river carrying during any time t , m^3 ; γ is the volume mass of the fetches, kg/m^3 .

The volume of the total space between the rehabilitation facilities built in the river whose channel is restored is W

$$W = bhl, \quad (3)$$

where b is the width of the channel, m ; h - the depth of lowering of the channel due to washing or quarries (thickness of the erosion layer), m ; l is the length of the restored channel, m .

We get equating expressions (2) and (3)

$$W_g = W = bhl = \frac{G}{\gamma} t. \quad (4)$$

We get solving equation (4) with respect to t

$$t = \frac{\gamma W}{G}, \quad (5)$$

where t is the recovery period of the channel, *day*; W - is the total volume of the space between the devices built in the renewable channel, m^3 ; γ - volume mass of the materials, kg/m^3 ; G - is the average long-term fetches of water, m^3/day .

Let's turn to a concrete example.

The channel of the Goychay River completely lost its stability in the distance $B=4.5$ km from the second fixer to the Baku-Kazakh highway, and the bottom of the river dropped 10 m below the initial level. In this part of the river, its width is 30 m. According to long-term hydrometric observations, the average value of solids consumption of the river is $G=2.7$ kg/sec= 233280 kg/day. In the eroded part of the river, the slope is 0.005.

According to these actual values, we take the height of the bottom sill or the net sewer rehabilitation device as $h=9$ m and determine the distance between the devices using the formula (1): $L=9/0.005=1800$ m.

We find the number of devices in the unstable river channel: $n=B/L=4500/1800=2.25$ units.

The facility is being built on two banks of the river.

Using the formula (3), we determine the volume of the space between the devices:

$$W=b h l=30 \cdot 9 \cdot 4500=1,215 \text{ mln } m^3.$$

Volumetric mass of river fetches is $\gamma=2,6$ $g/sm^3=2600$ kg/m^3 Based on the known values, we determine the recovery period of the channel using the formula (5): $t=2600 \cdot 1,215000/233280=13542$ *day* = $37,1$ *year*.

According to the calculations (forecast) made on the basis of concrete and actual data, it will take at least 37.1 years to restore the 4.5 km deformed (washed) course of the Goychay River to its original state. If the river naturally recovers its course, it will take at least 100 years to recover.

The role of torrent flows in the rehabilitation process of the channel. Torrent flows have a great role in restoring the course of rivers that have lost their natural stability as a result of the activity of quarries and other anthropogenic effects on rivers. The consumption of solids during torrent flows varies from 25 kg/s to 380 kg/s. According to long-term experiments carried out on the Goychay River, the consumption of solids in this river is 44-200 kg/s [14]. It is possible to restore the channel in a short period by holding the hard joints in the deformed channel with channel restoration devices.

At this time, the amount of solids carried by the flood at one time takes a very large value and is determined by the following expression:

$$m = 3600 GT, \quad (6)$$

where m is the amount of solids carried by the flood, *kg*; G - consumption of solids, *kg/sec*; T is the duration of a single flood, *hours*.

In the absence of channel restoration devices, a small part of the sediment settles in the river, and most of it is carried by the torrent flow and enters the river banks and the river sediment cone. If these sediments are caught in the bottom channel restoration devices, then large amounts of solid sediments will settle into the channel.

If we assume that the consumption of solids brought by the river is $G=120$ *kg/sec*, and the duration is $T=18$ hours, then according to the formula (6), the mass of solid materials carried by the flood at one time will be $m=3600 \cdot 18 \cdot 120=7.776$ million *kg*.

It shows that the washed and deepened river channel can return to its initial state in a short period due to the passage of the torrent. Under the condition that channel restoration bottom facilities have been operating in the deformed part of the river.

The result. 1. The proposed channel restoration bottom net has several advantages compared to known devices. So, this device has a lighter construction, is durable and reliable, and requires less material and labor for its construction. At the same time, it can work as a device that prevents or mitigates the destructive effects of torrent and flood water. It can be used in any condition.

2. Torrent flows play an important role in the rehabilitation process. Thus, the torrent water accumulates in the deformed river bed and ensures the restoration of the channel in a short time.

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